

TABLE FOR PRE/POST Q

Cat.	Categoria	when	#	Item	Dir.	1	5
A	Sustainable design in software engineering	Pre + Post	A1	I consider environmental impact when making software design decisions.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			A2	I consider social impact when making software design decisions.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			A3	I consider economic impact when making software design decisions.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			A4	Sustainability is not a priority for me when developing software.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			A5	I know how to evaluate the environmental footprint of a software system.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			A6	Environmental concerns are someone else's responsibility in software projects.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
B	Awareness of cognitive biases	Pre + Post	B1	I am aware that cognitive biases can influence my design decisions.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			B2	My design choices are always based on objective reasoning, not biases.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			B3	I can recognize when a bias might be affecting my project decisions.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			B4	I rarely question whether my assumptions about a project are correct.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
C	AI as a reflective tool	Pre + Post	C1	I believe AI tools can help me identify blind spots in my reasoning.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree

			C2	AI-driven questioning is not useful for improving design decisions.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			C3	A conversational AI can effectively support critical reflection on my work.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			C4	I would rather reflect on my decisions alone than with the help of an AI tool.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
D	Prior AI use & familiarity <i>(pre of F)</i>	Pre only	D1	I regularly use AI tools in my study or work.	→	Never	Daily
			D2	I feel confident using AI tools for technical tasks.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			D3	I find AI tools difficult to use effectively.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			D4	I have used conversational AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT) in the past six months.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
E	Use of AI in sustainability <i>(pre of G)</i>	Pre only	E1	I have used AI tools to address sustainability-related problems.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			E2	I believe AI has no meaningful role in making software more sustainable.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			E3	I am interested in tools that evaluate sustainability aspects of my work.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			E4	Sustainability and AI are topics I rarely connect in my practice.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
F	Usability & chatbot experience <i>(post of D)</i>	Post only	F1	The chatbot's questions were clear and easy to understand.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
			F2	I found the conversation with the chatbot confusing or hard to follow.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree

G	Future use intention <i>(post of E)</i>	Post only	F3	The chatbot's questions were relevant to my specific project.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree		
			F4	Interacting with the chatbot felt unnatural or forced.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree		
			G1	I intend to use AI reflection tools in future software projects.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree		
			G2	I would not use a tool like this again in my studies or work.	R	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree		
					G3	I think tools like BIAS should be integrated into SE curricula.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
					G4	After this experience, I feel more motivated to reflect on sustainability in my projects.	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
				Post only		I reconsidered assumptions I had not questioned before	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
						I noticed biases in my own reasoning during the interaction	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree
						How was your interaction with the AI chatbot? Were there any new insights for you?		Open question	
						Did the use of the chatbot help you explore ways to make your research/project more sustainable?		Open question	
						Any suggestions for improvement?		Open question	
						Please indicate the type of idea discussed		Open question	
				Pre only		What is your gender?			
						I am familiar with sustainability topic in software engineering	→	Strongly disagree	Strongly agree